

Semiclassical Approach to Quantum Oscillator Ground State Energy with Moyal Product

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The quantum oscillator ground state energy may be obtained by solving the time-independent Schrodinger equation and selecting the lowest energy eigenvalue. In (1) it is suggested that ground state oscillator energy appears in an semiclassical calculation of oscillator energy using the Moyal product (**) i.e. $(p+iwx) ** (p-iwx) .5 = pp/2 + wwxx/2 + \hbar w/2$ for $m=1$. In this note, we try to show that the Moyal product: $(p+iwx)/\sqrt{2}\{ d/dx (left)d/dp (right) - d/dp (left) d/dx (right) \} (p-iw)/\sqrt{2}$ follows from the fact that $W_0(x)$ and $a_0(p)$ where W_0 is the ground state wavefunction and a_0 the ground state momentum wavefunction have the same functional form and that this form is in fact a Gaussian so that $W_0(x)a_0(p) = \exp(-\text{constant}(pp/2 + wwxx/2))$. By using both, one may create a combined time-independent Schrodinger equation with both p and x present at the same time giving the appearance of a semiclassical approach. With respect to the ground state energy, $d/dx d/dx$ acting on a Gaussian $\exp(-axx-bpp)$ first brings down $2ax$ followed by $2a$ from the second derivative (and similar results for $d/dp d/dp$). The other part of the second derivative is x dependent and cancels the x dependent potential. Thus one may think in terms of a single derivative d/dx acting on ax or a single derivative acting on bp . Combining in a symmetric form leads to the Moyal product acting on $p+iwx$ and $p-iwx$ to yield the ground state oscillator energy. We argue that this is essentially the same information as the time-independent Schrodinger equation with the special Gaussian form of the ground state wavefunction. Thus derivatives essentially act on $pp/2 + wwxx/2$ in a product of the x -wavefunction and p -wavefunction and this may be converted into a scheme of single derivative acting on the variable $p+iwx$ and $p-iwx$ because the relative piece of the $d/dx d/dx$ of the Schrodinger equation is: $d/dx d/dx \exp(-axx) \rightarrow d/dx 2ax \exp(-axx) \rightarrow 2a$ (linear in a) with the other term of the second derivative canceling with $.5kxx \exp(-axx)$.

Moyal Product and Semiclassical Approach to the Quantum Oscillator

In (1) it is suggested that the Moyal product may be used to find the ground state oscillator energy while using classical variables i.e. using a semiclassical approach. In particular, the Moyal product is defined as:

$$** = f(p,x) \{ \exp i\hbar/2 [d/dx \text{ right } d/dp \text{ left} - d/dp \text{ right } d/dx \text{ left}] \} \quad ((1))$$

The energy of the oscillator is then written classically as:

$$\text{Energy} = (pp/2 + ww xx/2) = 1/2(p+ iwx) (p-iw x) \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where } w = \sqrt{k/m} \text{ with } m=1$$

Given the symmetry of x and p , the energy is written as a product of two terms containing x and p i.e. a new complex variable which multiplied by its conjugate yields energy

If $i\hbar/2$ is considered to be very small then the Moyal derivative ((1)) becomes:

$$\hat{H} = f(p,x) \{ 1 + \hbar/2 [d/dx \text{ right } d/dp \text{ left} - d/dp \text{ right } d/dx \text{ left}] \} g(p,x) \quad ((2))$$

In (1) the oscillator energy ((2)) is then written in terms of the $\hbar/N \ll 1$ limit of the Moyal product i.e.

$$\text{Energy} = (p+i\omega x)/\sqrt{2} \hat{H} (p-i\omega x)/\sqrt{2} \quad ((3))$$

((3)) is then said to contain classical variables x,p , but to also yield the ground state energy as ((3)) is equivalent to:

$$\text{Energy} = pp/2 + \omega\omega xx/2 + \hbar \omega/2 \quad ((4))$$

Quantum Mechanics and the Moyal Product

In (1) the Moyal product acts on the classical variables x and p . In quantum mechanics it is said that if one knows x exactly, one does not know p at all and vice versa. Thus, p and x do not appear in the same time-independent Schrodinger equation. They can, however, be made to appear if one uses a Schrodinger equation in the spatial wavefunction and another for the momentum wavefunction.

For the quantum oscillator, x - p symmetry dictates that the functional form of the ground state x and p wavefunctions should be the same. (This holds above the ground state as well.) Furthermore the ground state should represent the lowest energy state i.e. classically it is like placing the particle at $x=0$, thus one expects an even function in x i.e. in xx for the x -wavefunction. The p -wavefunction must then be a function of pp .

Next consider the time-independent Schrodinger equation in x and p spaces i.e.

$$-1/2m d/dx d/dx F(ax) + .5kxx F(ax) = E_0 F(ax) \quad ((5a))$$

$$pp/2m F(bp) - .5k d/dp d/dp F(bp) = E_0 F(bp) \quad ((5b)) \quad \text{where } a,b \text{ are constants}$$

Combining ((5a)) and ((5b)) yields:

$$bp / F(bp) = E_0 \quad ((7))$$

F is quadratic in its argument, but no p,x may appear on the LHS of ((7)), thus

$$D \ln(F(ax)) / dx + d \ln(F(bp)) / dp \text{ must} = \text{constant} (\omega\omega xx/2 + pp/2) = \text{constant} (E_0) \quad ((8))$$

This means that F is of the form: $\exp(-aaxx)$ and $\exp(-bbpp)$ such that $F(aaxx)F(ppbb) = \exp(-E_0 \text{ constant}) = \exp(-\text{constant} (pp/2 + \omega\omega xx/2))$. Thus one has the form of the ground state p and x wavefunctions i.e. Gaussians in x and p . In fact, the exact solutions are: $W_0(x) = \exp(-.5\sqrt{km} xx)$ and $W_0(p) = \exp(-.5 (1/\sqrt{km}) pp)$.

This means that: $d/dx d/dx \exp(-aaxx) = -aa^2 \exp(-aaxx) + 4aaaaxx \exp(-aaxx) \quad ((9))$ and a similar expression for p .

In ((6)), the second term on the RHS of ((9)) cancels $wxx/2$ and the same result holds for the second p term canceling $pp/2$.

As a result, the same result, of ((6)) could be obtained using:

$$d/dx \ 2ax = 2a \quad ((10))$$

In other words a single derivative acting on the classical variable x multiplied by a constant yields the quantum constant $2a$. This paves the way, we argue, for using the linear Moyal product which writes derivatives in a symmetrical fashion. If one has the variables:

$$P+iwx \quad \text{and} \quad p-iwx \quad (m=1)$$

Then d/dp brings back 1 and d/dx either $-iw$ or iw . $\hbar w / 2$ is the ground state energy and the $\frac{1}{2} \hbar w$ is part of the Moyal product definition (see ((2))). As a result, one simply wants the coefficients aa, bb and these may be obtained by taking first order derivatives of classical variables which have the same weights as the quantum result. Furthermore, the quantum result $\exp(-.5\sqrt{k}m \ xx) \exp(-.5pp/\sqrt{k}m)$ so that the product is equivalent to energy times a constant.

As a result:

$$E \text{ ground state oscillator} = (p+iwx) \ \hbar w / 2 \ [d/dx \text{ right } d/dp \text{ left} - d/dp \text{ right } d/dx \text{ left}] \ (p-iwx)$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, in (1) it is argued that the quantum ground state energy may be obtained using a semiclassical approach, writing the classical energy as: $E = (p+iwx) (p-iwx)$ (for $m=1$) and then rewriting this in the manner: $E = (p+iwx) ** (p-iwx)$ where $**$ is the Moyal product which is linear in the derivatives d/dx and d/dp .

The time-independent Schrodinger equation, on the other hand, uses second order derivatives e.g. $d/dx \ d/dx$. We argue that the wavefunction for the ground state must be of the form: $\exp(-aax) = \text{space wavefunction}$ and $\exp(-bbpp) = \text{momentum wavefunction}$ such that: $\exp(-aax-bbpp) = \exp(-\text{constant} (wxx/2 + pp/2))$. Thus the second derivative $d/dx \ d/dx$ breaks into two pieces with one yielding $-2aa \exp(-aax)$. This is the piece linked to energy because the second term cancels with $-k/2 \ xx \exp(-aax)$. $-2aa$, however, is a linear term in aa and so only a single d/dx is needed operating on $(p+iwx)$. Thus one may use a Moyal derivative linear in d/dp and d/dx acting on $(p+iwx) ** (p-iwx)$ in order to obtain the ground state oscillator energy. The product x -wavefunction and p -wavefunction yield $\exp(-\text{constant} (p+iwx)(p-iwx))$. This approach appears to be semiclassical, but it really mimics the behaviour of the combined time-independent Schrodinger equations in x -space and p -space.

References

1. De Antrade, M.A. et al. Noncommutative Derivation of Planck's Radiation Law (2023)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2304.02067.pdf>